

Pinagpala

PUBLISHING SERVICES

Camia St., Blk. 6, Brgy. San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines
 DTI Reg. No. 3034433 (National)/ BIR TIN No. 293-150-678
 Business Permit No. 8183
 pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com/ +639985799958
 National Book Development Board Reg. No. 3269

ARTICLE PUBLICATION EVALUATION/ PEER-REVIEW RESULT

Title of Work/s: "Cultivating Executive Function Skills in Early Childhood Education: A Narrative Review of Theoretical Foundations and Classroom Practices"			
Publication: World Education Connect Multi-Disciplinary e-Publication Volume V, Issue XI, Nov. 2025			
Date Reviewed: Nov.5, 2025			
The information below consists of the summary of article publication evaluation/peer review results conducted by Pinagpala Publishing Services prior to the publication of the article:			
Areas for Evaluation/Review:	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
Relevance of the contents to the topic	✓	✓	✓
Organization of the ideas presented	✓	✓	✓
Originality of the Material	✓	✓	✓
Other technical aspects (language used, accuracy and timeliness of the information)	✓	✓	✓
No. of Areas Achieved:	4	4	4
Decision:	ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION		
<i>*Legend: 4 Areas Achieved: Accepted for Publication, No Revisions Needed 3 Areas Achieved: Minor Revisions Needed Before the Publication 2 Areas Achieved: Major Revisions Needed Before the Publication 1-0 Areas Achieved: Not Accepted for Publication</i>			

Pinagpala Publishing Services Evaluators/Reviewers:

Reviewer 1

Reviewer 2

Reviewer 3

Note: PPS uses the double-blind peer review and evaluation where both reviewers and authors are unaware of each other's identities to mitigate the risk of prejudice on the side of the reviewers.

Certified Correct:

BLESSEY M. CERVANTES, EdD.
 Chief Executive Editor

+639985799958

pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing